

AVIONICS ARCHITECTURES
FOR THE NEXT GENERATION OF LAUNCH VEHICLES

JEFFREY H. STANLEY
WRIGHT RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT CENTER
AVIONICS LABORATORY, WRDC/AAAS-1
WRIGHT-PATTERSON AIR FORCE BASE, OHIO 45433

SUMMARY

Present avionics system architectures suitable for space launch vehicles are leading to growing costs due to unique subsystems and components, single source manufacturers, expanding ground operations and checkout, and increasing software maintenance. In addition, the inability of these systems to perform the required functionality and reliability needed to maintain mission cost effectiveness falls far below what is needed for future systems. Space vehicle programs such as the Advanced Launch System (ALS), Expendable Launch Vehicle (ELV), National Aerospace Plane (NASP), and future Shuttle derivatives are considered likely candidates for the insertion of new technologies and concepts. Current systems, such as the Delta and Titan series, can benefit from this technology influx as well.

This paper discusses the challenges and benefits of utilizing the same avionics architecture concepts which current and future military aircraft avionics are leading towards. The generic integration approach and architecture produced by the Advanced System Avionics (ASA) - PAVE PILLAR program is the foundation for avionics development in next generation aircraft for the U.S. Department of Defense and include aircraft such as the USAF Advanced Tactical Fighter (ATF) and USN Advanced Tactical Aircraft (ATA). The implementation strategies which are being employed by aircraft avionics include the system-wide utilization of common modular building blocks using advanced microelectronics such as VHSIC, Standard Electronic Module (SEM) sizes and integrated racks, and interconnection networks using fiber optics.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, cost and weight considerations have dictated a single string avionics architecture for expendable launch vehicles, such that a single failure could be mission catastrophic. The advent of more complex systems, costly payloads, and of man-in-space ratings require greater reliability, leading to increased redundancy and its management. The next generation avionics suite and its supporting software must extend beyond present switching logic and majority voting techniques to provide multiple fail-operational configurations in near real-time. The Avionics Laboratory has been pursuing a technology program to define a modular fault tolerant avionics architecture to support the next generation of launch vehicles in the 1990s. The Multi-Path Redundant Avionics Suite (MPRAS) program is striving to increase the avionics reliability and performance while lowering the maintenance and life cycle costs of the launch vehicle process.

PAVE PILLAR

The increased use of advanced electronics has given modern combat aircraft phenomenal levels of performance, but at a stiff price in initial cost, maintenance workload and aircraft availability. In order to combat these demands, the Avionics Laboratory initiated the PAVE PILLAR program to develop concepts for the next generation integrated avionics system architectures. By disposing of traditional subsystem boundaries (i.e., flight control, navigation, mission management, electronic warfare, etc.), coupled with the advent of new technologies (VHSIC, Fiber Optics, Ada, etc.), the architecture was allowed to be integrated at a system level. The integration philosophy permits resources (processing, control) to be shared across traditional subsystems, thereby improving the system's accuracy, increasing its immunity to failure, and decreasing its reliance on multiple sensors. Several technological elements are being incorporated in the system: modular VHSIC signal and data processors (16 and 32 bit), fiber optic data busses with distributed control protocol, Ada distributed operating system, Sensor and Video Data Distribution Networks (SDDN, VDDN), and integrated diagnostic hardware and software. A system level view of the PAVE PILLAR architecture is given in figure 1.

The approach is to design the maximum amount of the avionics system from a small set of "building blocks" called common modules comprised of Very High Speed Integrated Circuits (VHSIC). A module contains the circuitry to perform the required digital processing function including interface control and health diagnosis. These modules are being designed

with stringent requirements for both extremely low failure rates and high fault detection and fault isolation capabilities. The goal is to detect and isolate faults to the module level with a high degree of confidence so that it will be possible to reconfigure the common shareable processing assets and continue the mission unperturbed. This is accomplished through the application of spare signal and data processors at the system level so that backup services are provided should the primary sources fail. In addition, the architecture supports graceful degradation in that when spare resources are exhausted remaining resources can be assigned to the highest priority functions on a mission basis. The failed modules are recorded and can be replaced later on the flight line with minimal or no test equipment needed, thereby utilizing a two-level maintenance concept.

This building block approach permits not only the initial development of a highly flexible avionics suite, but also the continued development and integration of Pre-Planned Product Improvements (P3I). This is accomplished within the architecture by the concept of standard data busses (Parallel Interface (PI), Test and Maintenance (TM), High Speed Data Bus (HSDB) and networks (SDDN, VDDN, Data Flow). This concept is implemented by Form, Fit, Function and Interface (F3I) specifications for each module type thereby permitting different designs by vendor for each module type and specific vendor module design modification dependent upon technological improvements. Due to the technology transparency of the architecture, as building blocks are identified they can readily be integrated into the avionics system thus permitting the performance upgrade at a relatively low cost.

AVIONICS THRUSTS

In addition to PAVE PILLAR, several thrusts to provide modular capabilities for existing avionics systems are underway, and new investigations have already begun in order to implement future technologies (year 2005) into the architecture. The Joint Integrated Avionics Working Group (JIAWG), Modular Avionics System Architecture (MASA) working group, and AVionics Integrity Program (AVIP) are all strong consortiums of industry and government personnel working towards the goals of standardization, commonality, and high reliability throughout modular integrated avionics. Under congressional mandate, the JIAWG process is a joint effort to develop common avionics between the Army Light Helicopter Family (LHX), Navy ATA, and Air

Force ATF for the weapon system programs. The JIAWG process is implemented through a family of supporting specifications for hardware modules, software modules and engineering environments, and architectural features such as built-in diagnostics. Complementing this weapon system specific activity is the MASA effort. The MASA program has been specifically formed to extend the applications of modular avionics developed and promulgated as standards by the JIAWG to other systems. It provides an open forum for industry to propose and develop improvements/extensions to the JIAWG/PAVE PILLAR architecture independent of the weapon system programs. The applicability of modular avionics to current inventory aircraft (retrofit) and space systems are examples of types of applications being explored. The AVIP programs thrust is to characterize the basic failure mechanisms associated with avionics systems in order to better understand and specify processes and implantation mechanisms that will lead to much higher reliability and maintainability.

Avionics technologies for future systems and avionics "upgrades" for the 21st century are currently being explored in the PAVE PACE initiative. Parallel processing, wafer scale integration, and concurrent software engineering are some of the technologies that are currently being explored in order to make avionics more affordable and available. This and several efforts are underway to take advantage of DARPA's Strategic Computing Initiative to implement the necessary high speed processing capabilities in a standard module, thus taking advantage of the existing framework of the PAVE PILLAR architecture.

INTEGRATION

Current launch vehicle avionics systems, as shown in figure 2, are constrained by the level of integration and the lack of synergism of the related components among the different subsystems and functional areas. This, in part, is due to low level of technology that is being employed and partially, because of the traditional subsystem and political boundaries in the vehicle design and modification itself. Beside the weight and cost constraints inherent to most avionics systems, single string designs were incorporated in many expendable vehicles for other factors. Since the mission timelines are relatively short, the probability of failure was acceptable versus the cost of the payload. Also, the ability to provide the necessary fault tolerant aspects to the avionics (i.e., fault detection,

isolation, reconfiguration) was not available during the initial design process. Today's expensive payloads, in conjunction with the need to eliminate the "standing armies" of ground operations, necessitate the need for a greater level of health monitoring capability coupled with a high degree of reliability. In order to achieve this goal in a cost effective manner, not only does the level of integration need improvement, but a life cycle cost infrastructure for the avionics must be established. The Multi-Path Redundant Avionics Suite (MPRAS) program was established to accommodate the growing requirements upon the launch vehicle avionics architecture and to take advantage of the advances made by the aircraft avionics industry.

To go beyond the level of integration that is currently implemented in today's launch vehicle avionics, the system must be functionally and physically repartitioned in order to take advantage of the new technologies evolved. Typical functional areas for the avionics have been guidance, navigation, control (engine, thrust vector, attitude, instrumentation), propellant pressurization, communication, vehicle sequencing and power distribution. Health monitoring capabilities throughout the vehicle, coupled with the off-loading of traditional ground tasks, have given rise to new functions and capabilities for the avionics system. This new partitioning of the system must not only meet the performance aspects of the vehicle, but the needs of lower cost and streamlined processing of the vehicle before, during, and after launch.

After the functional decomposition of the avionics has occurred, the communication, processing, and command flows of the vehicle can be integrated and utilize the modular processing and communication facilities afforded by modern aircraft avionics systems. Separate and unique interfaces will need to be disposed of in order to accomplish this. This can be accomplished by adopting the increasing number of standardization efforts in the areas of connectors and communication networks initiated by various technical societies such as the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE). However, the space community must be involved with the many ongoing processes in the avionics technical areas to ensure that the proper requirements are met within their mission realm. Implementations such as a standard digital interface between components will result in several benefits. Data transmission capabilities with the use of standard data busses such as fiber optic implementations Mil-STD-1773 and High Speed Data Busses will allow higher data rates and improved

environmental compatibility. The coupling of traditional subsystems such as guidance, navigation, and control (GN&C) with the propulsion system and functions such as on-board avionics processing with launch and ground support operations are examples of these. Figure 3 shows the functional interfaces of an MPRAS architecture.

Several new system level interfaces will evolve, not only to take advantage of the new communication and technologies to be employed, but to accommodate the physical partitioning inherent to the vehicle design. Geographical considerations must be made, for example, for the health monitoring sensors throughout the vehicle. When there is a significant amount of processing or instantaneous reaction to sensor data, a subsystem or processing site must be made to that site. Manufacturing considerations must be made in the partitioning process to allow for the support of testing subsystems and limiting connections between sections during the vehicle assembly process. Since the availability of the vehicle cannot suffer due to faults in the system, designs for the fault containment regions must be taken into consideration as well.

Guidance, Navigation, and Control

The primary function of the GN&C system is to achieve a precise injection of the vehicle into its required orbit. However, launch vehicles are not rigid systems and are under tremendous strains from gravitational and inertial forces. Past and current GN&C parameters have been developed on the ground prior to each mission and are based on expected natural forces that are to be encountered during the flight. These parameters are specific to each mission, and therefore, the need exists to verify and validate each launch, which is a very man-intensive task. Real-time mission control is needed to provide the onboard navigation models updates and to track, monitor, and handle contingencies should they occur.

Although there are very few hardware changes from mission to mission, there is a large recurring analysis task. Figure 4 shows a representative testing and development timeline for flight programs. This usually involves changes to flight constants in the software which may take many months of engineering analysis to calculate exactly what the vehicle must do for a particular payload. The limitations in current systems to accomplish this task on-board is constrained by the level and amount of processing capability that the avionics systems possess. Sensing and adapting to forces while in-

flight, then subsequently initiating the proper propulsion and control surface commands requires high performance communication and processing resources to be closely integrated together. The ability of the avionics processing to facilitate an autonomous GN&C system is certainly within the processing capabilities of an MPRAS-type system. The scheduled GN&C processing upgrade aboard the Atlas/Centaur vehicle is expected to be the Inertial Navigational Unit (INU). While providing performance, weight, and volume improvements over existing systems, the cost and technical capabilities of a MPRAS common module approach is certainly justifiable. A common module approach providing the same functionality can reasonably reduce the cost of the function by about one-fifth, while providing additional capabilities and growth potential. The ability of an MPRAS type system to "buy" its way onto the vehicle (mainly due to weight and LCC tradeoffs) should be offset by the vehicles ability to have a "launch on demand" availability.

HEALTH MONITORING

A health monitoring capability for the on-board systems has been deemed a major cost saving strategy for the avionics system. In order for this to be an efficient cost saving tool, the fault or anomaly must be able to be isolated to a particular subsystem component. This requires the health monitoring to be an integral part of the vehicle design, as well as, the entire launch process. Several functional areas and processes throughout the vehicle system launch cycle can be reduced due to health monitoring of the avionics. Figure 5 shows the functional interfaces that a health monitoring system would need to exhibit.

By utilizing a single digital interface for all the test assemblies, the use of special purpose Ground Support Equipment (GSE) would be eliminated. Components would be tested through normal connections on the vehicle, unlike the special hookups required during today's on-ground tests. These would also require sufficient capabilities for isolating faults to the correct side of the interface. Currently to check connector integrity, personnel are required to push-pull every pin and connector. Problems arise due to the fact that this type of testing can add additional errors into the system.

The navigation electronics have suffered due to the high initial cost of the systems and the amount of attention needed to verify the systems' precise working order. Factory, preflight, and on-pad

alignments and calibrations are major cost drivers in this area. Many of these subsystems are tested, tested again, tested once more, because there is a concern that any movement of the vehicle can cause a slight mis-alignment of the sensors or failure to a box. Automation of the testing and calibration of the navigational instruments through the launch cycle can be accomplished by the on-board avionics to reduce this cost burden.

The health monitoring system must be capable of detecting anomalies in vehicle subsystems that are typically not electrical components such as propulsion, structures, and hydraulic subsystems. The integration of existing propulsion health monitoring techniques with the avionics seems to be a logical progression from a technology and cost standpoint. The separation of propulsion and avionic electronics can no longer be financially supported by the launch vehicle community. Engine controller hardware designs can be realized with the same type of common module approach as the avionics to support low hardware costs and promote standardization and commonality. Critical engine health parameters and propulsion subsystem measurements such as various pressure, temperature, flow, position, and vibration can be communicated to the avionics and coupled with GN&C data to more effectively control the stability and flight of the vehicle.

It has been determined through past experience on such vehicles as the Atlas, Atlas/Centuar, Titan/Centuar, and Shuttle that the non-avionics subsystems are the largest cost drivers in the launch vehicle processes. Areas of high non-avionics costs include launch and ground support facilities, propellant systems, and ground and airborne subsystems checkout. By integrating the on-board avionics processing and health monitoring functions with the ground based operations considerable cost savings can be obtained. The capability for accomplishing this comes from the intrinsic architecture and technology usage. Current launch system avionics cannot currently process or assimilate the huge amount of information to accomplish this task. By automating certain traditional "ground" tasks and processing them on-board the multitudes of support personnel needed could be dramatically reduced. However, the change in many ground operations improvements requires not only changes in other subsystems and avionics, but changes in the traditional ground operation process. Therefore, one must realize that the avionics are only enabling technologies to support the required goals of cost and automation.

FAULT TOLERANCE

One of the thrusts of the MPRAS was to design into the architecture a high degree of fault tolerance in order to achieve high availability and reliability for launch and mission success. Fault tolerance is the ability of the system to maintain operation with faults. The fault tolerance scheme employed by the MPRAS architecture relies on its ability to detect, isolate, and contain faults within the specified fault containment regions of the system (a health monitoring function). The use of hardware and software design diversity is used to provide the system with the desired level of reliability. Hardware concepts such as redundant bussing, pooled sparing, hot and cold standby of redundant elements, self-checking circuitry, and built-in-test are used within the architecture. Software techniques involved include the use of operational software to detect, confine, and correct software data and timing errors during the systems operation.

Since the cost of standing down or delaying the vehicle during the ground operations (especially launch pad operations) can result in a loss of millions of dollars, the ability of the system to launch with a failure (availability) must be high. Whether or not the system will be launched with a known failure is unknown, but the reliability of the system must maintain a high degree of reliability with a known fault. With the increasing cost of payloads, the cost of unreliability is just as high.

In order to decrease the cost of the avionics hardware, the MPRAS contractors examined the reliability associated with the cost of reusing the avionics by way of a Propulsion/Avionics module. Figure 6 shows a selected mission scenario to deliver up to 150,000 lbs of payload to a 150 nm orbit to several standard inclinations. Reuse of the avionics puts a tremendous burden on the continued reliability of the system to function properly in order to meet the specified avionics reliability requirements of returns the majority of the avionics hardware, the reliability of the hardware must be high enough to preclude total refurbishment after every mission.

This increase in reliability per flight versus the cost of the avionics (cost of redundancy) lead to the examination of using a lower grade of electronics parts. Current launch vehicle avionics utilize Space qualified parts (class "S"). This type of part incurs greater costs due to the quality screening processes that they are required to meet. JIAWG type

common modules utilize the class "B" type military part. The cost of a class "S" part is 13 times as much as a class "B". The MPRAS trades showed that very little reliability is gained by going from one class of parts to the other when applied in redundant configurations. In conjunction with this, trades were done on the environmental differences for the launch vehicle environment to that specified for the JIAWG module set. Figure 7 shows the differences between some of the key environmental factors. Of these requirements, atmospheric pressure and temperature cycling is significantly different. Further analysis on the packaging effects will need to be accomplished, especially for the effects upon the enclosures and racks.

OPERATIONS

Since actual hardware costs of the avionics is a small percentage of the total LCC costs of the vehicle, the reduction of costs have to come from areas other than avionics. Therefore, the avionics must support and handle many traditional operations tasks to support these cost reductions. Operations from an avionics standpoint include the mission planning and development, hardware/vehicle integration and tests, data processing and analysis, and mission control. During the vehicle integration the avionics must support the verification of working systems and interfaces. The avionics must support the changes and enhancements of the software and flight programs based upon the mission and payload differences, as well as, inflight GN&C anomalies. The avionics must serve as the communication center of the mission control tasks and telemetry uplinks during the flight phase.

SUMMARY

The PAVE PILLAR core architecture objectives of high availability, resiliency, supportability and low life cycle cost are similar to the desired attributes of future space launch vehicles. The core avionics, with tailoring to space requirements, can be used as the design baseline for application to launch vehicles and thereby utilize the experience and investment already committed to the advanced modular avionics architecture program.

REFERENCES

1. Boeing Aerospace and Electronics. Multi-Path Redundant Avionics Suite, USAF Contract F33615-87-C-1477.
2. General Dynamics Space Systems Division. Multi-Path Redundant Avionics Suite, USAF Contract F33615-87-C-1478.

FIGURE (1) Advanced Avionics Architecture

FIGURE (2). Modern Launch Vehicle Avionics System.

FIGURE (3) MPRAS Functional Block Diagram

	NEW SYSTEM			REOCCURRING BASIS		
	MONTHS	MAN-YRS	COMPUTER HOURS	MONTHS	MAN-YRS	COMPUTER HOURS
FLIGHT PROGRAM	36	50	52000	3	1.5	200
TICS	24	5	3470	3	1	695
DFAST	9	3	6240	1	0.5	1040

FIGURE (4). Testing and Development Times for Flight Programs.

FIGURE (5) Vehicle Health Monitoring System Functional Interrelationships

FIGURE (6) Example Mission Scenario

Parameter	JIAWG Standard (proposed)	MPRAS
Vibration	20g (20-2000Hz) MIL-STD-810	11g rms
Shock	Nom. 20g (11ms) Max. 100g (6ms)	10g (landing)
Pyrotechnic Shock		>1000g@1KHz (separation)
Acoustic	<165dBA	<165dBA Outside <155dBA Inside
Atmospheric Pressure	760 - 8 mmHg	931 - 10 mmHg -10
Temperature Range	Store -62° to 125°C Op. -54° to 60°C 95°C for 30 min.	Store -54° to 93°C Op -54° to 71°C
Humidity	0-100%	0-100%
Salt Fog	5% salt @ 35°C for 48 hours	5% salt @ 35°C for 48 hours

FIGURE (7) Environmental Factors